

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

INITIAL SET OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

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TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

D6.2 – INITIAL SET OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

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Executive Summary

ENERGIZE project is cofounded by the European Commission through the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program. ENERGIZE aims to demonstrate the potential of cooperative energy models in industrial zones across the EU. These initiatives face considerable challenges -especially in governance, legal frameworks and financial sustainability- which ENERGIZE aims to overcome. It will promote energy collaboration through active engagement, capacity building, and the creation of a dedicated digital hub to serve as a support tool. This approach will foster renewable energy projects, resource efficiency, and circularity within these communities.

This document outlines the comprehensive suite of communication and dissemination materials developed for ENERGIZE. It includes the project's visual identity, a flyer detailing its primary objectives and goals, a roll-up banner for events, and an operational landing webpage designed to facilitate information exchange.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
LIFE CET	LIFE Clean Energy Transition

1 Introduction

The communication and dissemination activities are included as part of Work Package 6, in particular of “Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination of ENERGIZE Project”, which centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of project’s communication and dissemination activities. Task 6.1 consists of different subtasks:

- T6.1.1: Communication, dissemination and engagement plan and coordination
- T6.1.2: Communication material and tools, which includes:
 - Project brand and visual identity
 - Landing webpage and blog
 - Project brochure
 - Communication videos
- T6.1.3: Dissemination activities and communication campaigns, which includes:
 - Social media
 - Press releases and newsletter
 - Communication campaigns
 - Site visits
 - Participation in public events
 - Networking with other LIFE projects
 - Final ENERGIZE International Workshop

This document shows the initial set of general communication and dissemination activities of the project, in particular those that have been developed within the first 6 months of the project, in line with the ENERGIZE Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan of the project.

2 Visual identity

ENERGIZE project has developed a Visual Identity Handbook that will constitute the main reference regarding the graphical layout of the different communication and dissemination materials (e.g. website, deliverables, press releases, presentations). The Visual Identity Handbook includes several key parts:

- Logo, in different versions to maximise compatibility with other communication frameworks.
- Colours and typographies to be prioritised.
- Template for deliverables.
- Template for slideshows and presentations.

The Visual Identity Handbook is a private report for consortium partners, but the main outcomes are shown in next sections.

2.1 Logo

The logo plays an important role in the project, because it will represent the identity of ENERGIZE project in all the different communication materials. It is part of all the deliverables and makes the project recognisable.

The logo has been designed to emphasize “energy” aspects of the project. Thus, the basic colours are different degradations from blue – usually associated to energy – and a lightning icon has been integrated within one of the letters of the logo.

Figure 2-1 – Logo, main version

The logo can be presented in different additional formats – compact, rounded, horizontal – and colour variation – solid black, negative blue – depending on the specific needs of the communication material. For instance, social networks such as LinkedIn or X require two profile pictures, a small one and a long horizontal one. All of them follow a similar approach on the use and combination of colours.

Figure 2-2 – Logo, compact and rounded versions

Figure 2-3 – Logo, horizontal version

Figure 2-4 – Logo, additional colour chart

2.2 Primary colour palette

The ENERGIZE logo uses a set of colours that can be combined in different ways.

Figure 2-5 – ENERGIZE palette of colours

2.3 Slides template

Different slides have been defined, to maximise the compatibility of the logo and the palette of colours with the overall readability of the content.

Figure 2-6 – Templates for initial, text, and final slides

2.4 Deliverable template

Project deliverables need to respect some specific requirements from the European Commission. A specific template for ENERGIZE deliverables has been created in MsWORD, aiming to define a common graphical layout framework respecting these EC requirements and increasing the coherence within all the deliverables that will be prepared during project duration.

Furthermore, the proposed template includes initial and final pages that could be used for communication and dissemination purposes, following a “magazine” style, removing the codename of the deliverable, and enhancing the aesthetics of the document.

Figure 2-7 – Template for the deliverable, initial and last pages

3 Website

The main objective of the ENERGIZE landing page is to serve as the vehicle for the communication and dissemination of project activities and outcomes.

While the web page has been publicly available since mid-October 2024, with an initial simple version (“home”, “news” and “contact” sections, only in English), the version at the end of December 2024 is already fully operational. It is available at: www.energizcommunity.eu.

The ENERGIZE website has been defined to be user-friendly and easy to use, with a smooth transition between the different sections and some transversal functionalities (e.g. social networks, contact form, news, language) that are present in different sections.

3.1 Languages

The ENERGIZE project mainly targets business and public authorities across Europe, but special emphasis is in the 4 pilot regions: Catalonia, Valsesia, Upper Austria and Zlín regions. So, while English will be the main communication and dissemination language, the website includes specific sections in Catalan, Czech, German, Italian and Spanish languages, to facilitate communication and dissemination in those regions.

3.2 Website structure

The website includes a tree structure following the 5 main sections to facilitate an easy access to the most useful information. Thus, the main sections defined in the website are:

Home – Our purpose – News – Resources – ENERGIZE Hub – Contact

At this moment, the “resources” section is not publicly available, because very few relevant public deliverables have been released. This section will be activated by the end of January 2024, aligned with the delivery of first relevant technical outputs.

The “ENERGIZE Hub” section will be developed following the progress of the platform development (WP3).

3.2.1 Home

The “Home” section includes some leitmotiv style description of ENERGIZE project ambition, followed by a visual representation of the types of partners involved and the geographical scope. It also includes a summary of the news section (highlighting the 3 most recent news), and a newsletter subscription form, in order to allow visitors to receive the periodic newsletter that the project will prepare.

3.2.2 Our purpose

The “Our Purpose” section allows the understanding of the ENERGIZE goals, objectives and impacts. A part from those aspects, this section includes also a visual representation of the pilot areas of the project, as well as detailed description of consortium partners, with links to their institutional webpages.

3.2.3 News

This section keeps the visitor informed about all the events and news of the project. The section includes a matrix-style view of the different news, chronologically sorted. A widget to follow ENERGIZE social media is also included, as well as the newsletter subscription form to allow visitors to receive the regular newsletters the project will prepare.

3.2.4 Resources

This section allows to easy find the most relevant public documentation created within the ENERGIZE project. From public deliverables to scientific papers or conference presentations, as well as webinars & workshops recordings (in direct link to the ENERGIZE YouTube channel). It also includes a link to the Zenodo ENERGIZE community, where the whole set of public deliverables will be available.

3.2.5 ENERGIZE hub

This section will allow stakeholders to get access to the ENERGIZE Hub that will be developed within WP3. So, at the moment of writing this document, the structure of this section is still under definition. We expect this section to be made public once the platform will be created, following WP3 progress.

3.2.6 Contact, social media and newsletter subscription

The website includes the usual contact section, together with specific high visibility icons to follow the project progress through the social media channels (in particular LinkedIn, X, Instagram and YouTube).

The newsletter subscription form has been also included, in order to allow interested stakeholders to receive the regular newsletters that the project will create during its duration.

3.3 Website screenshots

Several screenshots of the website are included within this document. The whole website can be accessed through: www.energizemcommunity.eu .

Figure 3-1 – “Home” section (partial view)

Figure 3-2 – “Our purpose” section (partial view)

Figure 3-3 – “News” section (partial view)

Figure 3-4 – Pilot region’s language examples (partial view)

4 Flyer

A project flyer has been designed to serve as the primary promotional material, featuring a concise description of ENERGIZE's objectives and anticipated impacts.

To address one of the common challenges of such materials—being discarded shortly after being read—the flyer was crafted with a focus on aesthetic appeal and functional design. Drawing inspiration from the Bauhaus movement, which influenced some of the most iconic International Expositions of the early 20th century, the flyer combines striking visuals with clear, engaging content to ensure lasting impact and retention. Additionally, the flyer features a small section on the back designed for taking quick notes.

The flyer has been created in English and then translated to the local languages of the four ENERGIZE demo sites (Catalan, Czech, German and Italian).

4.1 Visual aspect

Figure 4-1 – Front page of the flyer

Figure 4-2 – Reverse page of the flyer

Figure 4-3 – Pilot region’s language versions (CZ, CAT, IT, DE)

5 Roll-up

A specific roll-up has been designed for increasing the project visibility at fairs and conferences, or for other project events. This roll-up provides a clear and simple introduction to the project, showcasing social media channels and involved partners.

Figure 5-1 – Roll-up (2024 version)

More information: www.energizcommunity.eu

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